

Application of Coordination Compounds of Silicon and Copper in Fiber and Fiber Reinforced Plastic Materials

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Some of the important characteristics of fiber reinforced plastic materials which make them significant as high specific strength, stiff, corrosion and fatigue resistant materials, have been described. Use of coordination compounds of copper and silicon has been particularly mentioned in view of their marked effect in increasing the strength of fibers in the case of carbon fibers and interfacial bonding between fiber and matrix for glass fiber reinforced plastics, respectively. The coordination compounds of monovalent copper such as dichloro and diacetato and of silicon mainly aminosiloxanes help in cyclisation reaction resulting in considerable increase in the mechanical properties of carbon fibers formed which is ultimately reflected in the composite properties. The silicon coupling compounds having organic functional groups coordinated to silicon give, on treatment with a glass fiber, a relatively high surface energy which gives good wetting as well as bonding to the resinous matrix.

FIBER reinforced plastics¹⁻⁵ are finding increasing use as structural engineering materials because of their high strength and stiffness properties varying over a broad range. Carbon fibers and glass fibers have been extensively used in reinforced plastics for use in industrial applications such as aerospace, chemical, mechanical, marine, sports, agricultural and medical. The glass fiber reinforced composites are comparatively cheaper compared to carbon fiber reinforced plastics (CFRP) but have low specific stiffness. On the other hand CFRP have high specific stiffness which is maintained even at higher temperatures²⁻⁶. During the past two decades, tremendous efforts have been made to develop stiff reinforcing fibers and FRP materials⁷⁻¹⁰. New methods and techniques have been developed to make high strength high modulus carbon fibers. Newer compositions of thermosetting resins such as epoxy, phenolic and polyester and thermoplastic resins such as some polyester, polyethylene, polypropylene, nylon 6/6, etc. have been made to suit specific requirements of FRP industry.

Carbon fiber is a newer form of carbon obtained by pyrolysing different organic fibers which are polymeric in character. Most extensively used precursors for carbon fiber preparation are polyacrylonitrile (PAN), jute, rayon, pitch etc¹⁰. The characteristics of carbon fibers produced depend on the nature of precursor and processing conditions. During the past decade considerable research and development activity have been going on in NPL for producing carbon fibers from different precursors.

Carbon fiber manufacture involves two main steps¹¹:

1. Heat treatment in air or oxygen upto 300° to stabilize the precursor and convert the open chain structure of PAN to closed one.

2. Pyrolysis to 1000° in an inert atmosphere and heat treatment to 3000° in inert atmosphere, if desired.

The most critical step in the manufacture of carbon fiber is the oxidation step which controls the overall properties of the carbon fiber formed. For many years constant efforts are being made to control this step in order to cut short the treatment time and to save energy along with improvement in the mechanical properties of the ultimate carbon fibers². This can be brought about by incorporation of metallic additives in the form of coordination compounds such as dichloro or diacetato complexes of monovalent copper and aminosiloxane^{12,14}.

The oxidation step is done to produce thermally stable fibers so that they may not fuse when subjected to higher temperature. When pure PAN fiber is thermally treated in an inert atmosphere, the rearrangement of nitrile groups takes place at 200 to 300° giving a partially imperfect ladder type of cyclised structure represented by:

where *m* is generally in the range 0-2 and *n* in the range 0-5. This ladder type of structure is formed by free radical ionic mechanism. The free radicals are formed by the decomposition of defect structures in the precursor polymer. The amino radicals propagate and attack the next nitrile group or may abstract

a hydrogen atom terminating that particular resin has to be modified for effecting better adhesion and bonding. The study of adhesion is related to several known effects such as :

This rearrangement or oligomerization of nitrile groups can be initiated at a lower temperature and the cyclization reaction can be accelerated by incorporation of reagents such as organic acids, inorganic acids and bases and metallic salts.

These reagents broadly (i) lower the temperature of initiation of cyclisation reaction, (ii) convert the sharp and intense exotherm observed in case of pure PAN into broader one and the ΔT is reduced to a much lower extent¹⁴, (iii) the reagents provide a large number of initiation centers for cyclisation thereby the cyclisation takes place in a much shorter time and the extent of cyclisation is increased to a much larger value.

The cyclisation in presence of Lewis acids such as dichloro and diaceto monovalent copper ions takes place by ionic mechanism. The mechanism is shown below :

After the initiation, the reaction continues along the chain by stepwise ionic mechanism to produce ladder structure containing conjugated $-\text{C}=\text{N}-$ sequences. The fact that Cu is found in carbon fibers heated upto 1000° indicates that Cu is an integral part of carbon fiber.

By use of dichloro Cu complex in the processing of carbon from PAN, the first step treatment time has been reduced to one third of the normal treatment time without the use of coordination compounds. Moreover, it has been found that the tensile strength increases by 30% while the Young's Modulus by 50%¹⁵. This clearly indicates the effective role of copper complex in improving mechanical properties of carbon fibers.

To make use of the excellent mechanical properties of the fibers, they have to be incorporated into a suitable matrix system. The interface between the filler such as carbon fiber or glass fiber and the

1. Surface chemistry and physics of the components ;
2. The action of water and other potential weak bonding layers at the interface ;
3. The morphology of the matrix and the interface and
4. Mechanical requirements of the interface to allow distribution of shrinkages at areas of stress concentration.

In case of carbon fibers, oxide groups such as carbonyl, carboxyl, hydroxyl, etc. are incorporated on the fiber surface by surface treatment^{16,17} of the fibers, dry as well as wet. It involves treatment with oxygen, ozone, nitric acid, sodium hydroxide, sulphuric acid/potassium permanganate and different electrolytes such as hypochlorous acid, sodium hydroxide, etc.

In glass reinforced plastics, marked improvement in properties is imparted by traces of appropriate reactive silanes at the interface. This indicates that the silane coupling agents¹⁸⁻²³ have an important role which improves the adhesion. The silane coupling agents are of the general structure $\text{X}_3\text{Si}(\text{CH}_2)_n\gamma$ where n is 0-3, X is a hydrolysable group on silicon and γ is an organo functional group selected for compatibility with the given resin matrix. Most of the silane coupling agents are applied to glass fiber surface from aqueous solutions. The hydrolysable groups are therefore essential for generating intermediate silanols.

The compositions of silane coupling agents in dilute solutions depend on the organo functional groups and the pH of the solution. The silanes hydrolyse to give triols and then condense slowly to

oligomeric siloxanols.

Amino organo functional silane coupling agents show unique solution properties when nitrogen is on the 3-carbon atom. Since it is well known that the cyclic five or six membered chelate ring have extra stability, the low molecular weight siloxanes with internal-cyclic zwitter ion structures are formed in aqueous solution of three amino substituted organic silanols.

Therefore, all commercial amino functional silane coupling agents have the nitrogen atom on the 3-carbon atom.

The silane coupling agents are not generally deposited on the fiber surface as simple oriented mono molecular films, but as multilayers with variable orientation depending upon condition of deposition²⁰. A major portion of the deposited film is removed readily by water or organic solvents, but a small residue of the coupling agent is retained tenaciously by the surface which is effective in improving composite properties. Silanols, alkoxy silanes or chloro silanes applied to glass fiber under mild conditions are adsorbed physically through hydrogen bonding with surface silanol group. Under more strenuous conditions of temperature or catalyst the silanes bond chemically with the surface through siloxane linkages. These compounds are stable to air and water vapour. Another method of bonding chemically a coupling agent to the glass surface is to react with a difunctional Grignard reagent to give a firmly bonded organo functional group. Use of a flourinated glass surface is also known.

The chemical mobility of coupling agents attached to glass surface through hydrolysable bonds appears to be beneficial to composite properties. There is no correlation between polarity of silane or wettability of silane treated glass and the effectiveness of the silane coupling agent. For example, glass treated with chloropropyl silane coupling agent has a relatively high surface energy and is readily wetted by resins. Such treatment is ineffective with polyesters and phenolics but is quite effective with epoxides where chemical reaction is possible between the chloropropyl groups and the epoxy curing agent.

Wetting studies on silane treated glass are futile in arriving at the primary mechanism of adhesion through silane coupling agents since the interface

between coupling agent and resin disappears during preparation of composites. Better wetting will allow complete displacement of air from the glass surface and reduce the number of voids in the composite. The amount of silane coupling agent required on a glass surface to impart good mechanical performance to a glass resin composite is too small to be measured by analytical means. The use of radio active tracers has been made and it has been confirmed that the amount required for a proper silane to function as coupling agent is even less than the amount required of the silane to form a monomolecular layer on the glass surface. Silane coupling agents are equally effective when added as integral blends in resins. The silane, by coreacting with the polymer, modifies the morphology of the interface to improve stress transfer at the interface and resistance to water. This almost invariably involves a tightening up of the polymer structure through increased crosslinks and rigidity. Therefore, the silane should have maximum reactivity with the polymer.

The silane coupling compounds can be produced by a number of methods involving chemical interaction of silicon containing compounds with mineral acid and organic functional groups. Trichloro and tetrachloro silanes have been extensively used as starting material for interaction with the organic compounds for introducing organo functional groups in the structure. The conditions of the reaction depend on the type of coupling agent required. Trichloro and tetrachloro silanes have been prepared in NPL by interaction of ferro-silicon with mineral acid and then separating the two by methods of fractional distillation. The production and purification techniques have been standardised and the silanes have been prepared to the purity of 99.9%. The silanes were treated with alcohols and compounds of general formula $\text{Si}(\text{OR})_4$ and $\text{SiH}(\text{OR})_3$ were synthesised. The compounds are thermally stable. It is planned to prepare a number of organo-silicon derivatives from silane for use as coupling agents.

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